

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CURRENT SECURITIES IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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The globalization of the digital economy in the world has led to the acquisition of a modern and innovative character of securities operating in the economic space of the relevant organizations of any country. One of the main conditions for the development of modern financial instruments is economic innovation technologies. The digitization of the economy has led to the creation of new types of securities and the emergence of hybrid financial instruments that contain several financial instruments and have opened a wide avenue for their diffusion. This work analyzes the impact of modern innovation technologies on securities in the era of globalization of the digital economy. These innovative technologies have created more convenient and secure conditions for trading in the stock market and stock exchanges. This branch of the economy has also given rise to new professions such as internet trading and internet brokerage. With the development of economic circulation through the Internet, it became possible to monitor, purchase and sell classified securities, such as shares, bonds, futures, and promissory notes online through special Internet platforms. Today, securities, which are financial instruments issued by private joint-stock companies and joint-stock commercial banks, have become an integral part of the national economy. It has become possible to monitor bills online through special Internet platforms, to carry out operations such as buying and selling them [1]. "Ashgabat Stock Exchange" CJSC 2022 of stock held 2021 of 336130.6 (%) percent increase in comparison clearly testifies to this. And this is it shows that the emission and circulation of securities in our country is increasing [2].

SANLY_PAY.tm auxiliary web software (figure 1) was developed to analyze and monitor data on stocks, promissory notes, bonds, which are valuable securities of banks, joint-stock companies, industrial enterprises, economic organizations, based on modern innovative technologies.

Figure 1. The main window of the SANLY_PAY.tm web application

In this web application, the shares of "closed" and "open" types of joint stock companies are analyzed through the graphical method on different types of charts. Using a 2D coordinate system (figure 2), time t is represented on the horizontal axis, and the value G of the stock at a given time is represented by the coefficient on the vertical axis. The time function includes minute, hour, day, week, month, and year calendars.

Figure 2. SANLY_PAY.tm web application window

The main feature of the web program is that operations are carried out in the Turkmen language, and it is possible to determine the max, min and trend values of the function of securities belonging to one joint-stock company in real time and compare those values with shares of other joint-stock companies at the same time. In addition, geometric and dispersion functions are built into the web application indicator for thorough stock analysis. As a result of the investigations, a clear decision is made about the relevant stock, and the operation of selling or buying a valuable paper is carried out.

The development of modern innovative programs for smooth, functional and fast functioning of the securities market and their compatibility with other web programs and portals has become one of the most important issues of today.

As a result, one of the main conditions for solving the problem of continuous development of securities circulation and sustainable improvement of financial instruments in the conditions of the digital economy is the use of modern economic innovation technologies.

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